

CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND FIRM PERFORMANCE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF INDIAN COMPANIES

Mishu Tripathi

Thakur Institute of Management Studies and Research,
Mumbai, India. Email: mishutripathi1@gmail.com
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0441-6081>

Dr. Tariq Aziz

Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India.
Email: taziz.ba@amu.ac.in
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4528-840X>

Dr. Nirmala Joshi

Mumbai Educational Trust, Mumbai, India.
Email: dr.nirmala.s.joshi@gmail.com
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8319-8523>

Abstract

The research uses vigorous models on selected listed non-financial Indian companies of an index of National Stock Exchange (NSE) for a period of 21 years (2000-2020) to investigate the impact of capital structure on their performance. The empirical results reveal that all capital structure ratios (debt to equity, debt to market capitalization, and debt to total assets) significantly affect financial performance (return on assets, net worth, and Tobin's Q). Furthermore, age has a negative impact, total assets turnover has a positive impact and variables like cash flow, liquidity, fixed assets turnover, growth and size show mixed results on firm performance. The findings of this research are aligned with majority of researches conducted in emerging economies of Vietnam, Malaysia, Romania, Pakistan, Thailand and Ghana on similar theme. Due to shifting economic policies, regulatory landscape, and high yields in our country, leverage negatively impacts performance. Further, this study has important implications for financial managers when a decision on raising debt or equity capital is evaluated, for lenders while doing debt assessment, investors while making investment decisions and policy makers when designing capital.

Keywords: *Capital structure, Firm Performance, India, non-financial firms, listed, NSE*

1. INTRODUCTION

Any company's financial management is comprised of three primary decisions: investing, financing, and declaring dividends. Following an investment decision, the next step is to secure the necessary funding for the project. Debt or equity are the long-term instruments used to structure a company's capital structure, and these are the decisions that must be made. Capital structure refers to the mix of equity, debt, and retained earnings used to fund a company over the long term. Short-term funding sources are included in the decision to finance short-term capital requirements, and this is referred to as a financial structure. According to (Pandey 2015) the capital structure represents debt-equity ratios. Equity contains paid-up capital, share premium, reserves, and surplus."

In financial management, the capital structure decision is critical because it is focused on increasing shareholder wealth and the value of the company. Because the value of a firm is largely dependent on the firm's expected earnings and capital costs, the capital structure has a significant impact on the firm's value. Capital structure ratios must be carefully considered by management in order to minimise overall costs of capital, maximise earnings for owners, and thus maximise total firm value. The main theme of this research is to investigate the impact of capital structure on performance of firms in India of selected listed non-financial companies for a period of 21 years (2000-2020) using regression models and provide a solution to management in taking better capital structure decision.

The past researches in the area of capital structure and its impact on firm performance shows mix results. The studies conducted in the markets of Vietnam, Malaysia, Romania, Pakistan, Bangladesh shows a negative relationship between capital structure and firm performance while market of Thailand shows a positive relationship between them. The markets of Iran, Kenya and Nigeria shows positive relationship with short term debt and negative relationship with long term debt and market of Egypt shows no impact of capital structure on firm performance. Similar studies conducted in India, though limited, reflects the inverse relationship between capital structure and firm performance hence the current study was conducted to provide an extensive and detailed study on all the listed non-financial firms on NSE and shows the impact of capital structure on firm performance using regressions models.

The results of both the Fixed Effect Model and the Random Effect Model show that all capital structure ratios have a negative impact on firm performance and that the impact is significant only when the firm performance is measured by ROA and Tobin's Q. The results of the pooled regressions support this conclusion. The results are in consistent with the studies of (Le & Phan, 2017), (Sheikh & Wang, 2013), (Salim & Yadav, 2012) and (Saeedi & Mahmoodi, 2011) The study can be extended further to all the listed non-financial and financial firms in developing countries with long- and short-term measures of capital structure. The research paper is further divided into five sections where section 2 deals with detailed review of literature and section 3 provides the theoretical model of study and research methodology while section 4 explains results and discussions and the last session presents the conclusion of the study.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Firm characteristics with respect to capital structure

Cai & Zhang (2011) highlighted the importance of capital structure decisions in any firm and its effects on other decisions like financing, investment and strategic decisions, and also the wealth of shareholders. Strebulaev & Yang (2013) evidence from 1962 to 2009 showed that on an average 10.2 percent of large public non-financial US firms had eroded debt and nearly 22 percent had a book leverage ratio of less than 5%. The zero leverage firms pay significantly higher dividends, are more profitable, pay higher taxes, issue less equity, and have higher cash balances than the firms selected based on industry and size. The study also showed that firms with higher CEO ownership and longer CEO tenure, family firms are debt-free as compared to firms with smaller and independent boards.

2.2 Capital structure and Stock prices

Bhandari (1988) examined the association between predicted common stocks, Debt Equity Ratio

(DER), and BETA and size. DER significantly increased the predicted common stock returns of NYSE-listed corporations while Cai & Zhang, (2011) study showed that firm leverage ratio had a negative effect on stock prices of US listed non-financial firms. Another study of (Berggren et al., 2014) on Swedish companies showed that leverage had a positive effect on stock returns and results are consistent with Ullah & Shah (2014) study on companies listed on Karachi Stock Exchange. On the other hand Cai & Zhang (2006) studied the effect of changing leverage of U.S. public firms on stock prices and the result showed that firms with higher leverage changes had lower returns and Muradoğlu Yaz Gulnur & Sivaprasad, (2012) on UK firms showed lower leverage firms generate abnormal returns.

The study on listed Korean firms Yooa & Wu (2019) measures the relationship between capital structure and stock returns using structural equation model and the results revealed that stock returns have negative effect on capital structure with capital structure having no significant impact on stock returns. The similar insignificant relationship Michael Igbinovia & Marcella Ekwueme, (2022) is found with consumer goods firms listed on Nigeria stock exchange. Another study on FMCG companies listed on NSE and BSE Tetteh (2020) showed that capital structure (debt-to-equity ratio, return-to-equity ratio), firm performance (earnings per share) had a positive effect on stock returns.

2.3 Capital structure and Firm performance

A study on sample of Vietnam non-financial by Le & Phan (2017) showed that all debt ratios had a significant negative relationship with firm's performance which is same as Salim & Yadav (2012) study which had investigated the relationship between capital structure and firm performance of Malaysian listed companies across various sectors like construction, consumer product, industrial product, plantation, property, trading and service where the results indicated that firm performance had a negative relationship with short term debt, long term debt and total debt while it showed a positive relationship between the growth and performance for all the sectors and Tobin's Q also had a significant positive relationship with short term debt and long term debt. A study by Vătavu (2015) had established the relationship between capital structure and financial performance in Romanian companies operating in the manufacturing sector listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange and the findings showed that Romanian companies when avoid debt and operate on equity, their performance improves. Another study on non-financial Egyptian listed firms

El-Sayed Ebaid (2009) showed that capital structure choice has a weak-to-no impact on firm performance in Egypt. Similar study of Ahmed Sheikh & Wang (2013), Hasan et al. (2014) investigated the effect of capital structure on performance of non-financial firms in Pakistan and the result revealed that all measures of capital structure had a negative relation to return on assets. Further, the results of Pooled OLS model showed that the total debt ratio and long-term debt ratio are had a negative relation with market-to-book ratio, whereas in the fixed effects model, these measures had a positive relation with market-to-book ratio. In all regressions, the short-term debt ratio had a insignificant positive relation to the market-to-book ratio. Study on companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange Pouraghajan & Malekian (2012) showed that leverage had a negative impact on the financial performance and it also highlighted that by lowering the debt ratio, management can increase the company's profitability, financial performance and also the shareholder wealth. A study on Dhaka firms by Hasan et al. (2014) showed that EPS had a positive relation to short-term debt while a negative relation with long-term debt. On the other hand, ROA

and capital structure had a significant inverse relationship while no significant relationship with firm performance as measured by ROE and Tobin's Q. Further, a study of Robert et al. (2020) had examined the effect of capital structure on the performance of firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange and revealed that equity and long-term debt had a significant positive while short-term debt had a significant negative effect on the firm performance. Another study by Ayange et al. (2021) highlighted that the Nigerian manufacturing firms had a significant positive relationship between Tobin Q and short term and long-term debt but a negative relationship with total debt while Saeedi & Mahmoodi (2011) study investigated the relationship between capital structure and firm performance of the firms listed on Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) and the findings showed that firm performance, as measured by EPS and Tobin's Q, had a significant positive association with capital structure, while a negative relationship between ROA and capital structure. A study on non-financial firms in Thailand Detthamrong et al. (2017) highlighted that leverage had a positive effect on firm performance. A study on listed trading firms in Sri Lanka Niranjini & Priya (2013) showed a negative relationship between debt equity ratio and financial performance variables & positive relationship between debt asset ratio, long-term debt ratio and financial performance variables while Muraleetharan (2016) study on Beverage, Food and Tobacco companies in Sri Lanka showed that capital structure had a very little impact on the profitability of companies. Further, Abor (2005) found a positive association between short-term debt, overall debt, and ROE and a negative relationship between long-term debt and ROE in Ghanaian listed enterprises and a study on Jordanian companies Zeitun & Tian (2007) showed that firm's capital structure had a significant negative impact on the firm's performance measures and González (2013) highlighted that the leverage has negative effect on corporate operating performance across 39 countries.

2.4 Capital structure and Firm performance-Indian Studies

The presence of a threshold size dictated the non-linear relationship between capital structure and business performance, according to Jaisinghani & Kanjilal (2017) study on Indian manufacturing enterprises. Enterprises above the threshold size performed better with debt in capital structures. A study by Khanna & Srivastava (2013) showed that management efficiency affects the success of enterprises that issued stock during recession.

Dawar (2014) found that capital structure negatively affects firm performance, controlling parameters like size, firm age, tangibility, sales growth, liquidity, and advertising due to the underdeveloped Indian bond market and the dominance of state-owned banks in the Indian market, contradicting the agency theory of capital structure.

Chadha & Sharma (2015) and Rakesh M (2013) examined the impact of capital structure on financial performance of Indian manufacturing companies and BSE-listed business companies, respectively, and found that capital structure had no effect on Return on Asset and Tobin's Q but had a significant negative impact on Return on Equity. According to Chadha & Sharma (2015) size, age, tangibles, sales growth, asset turnover, and ownership structure also affect Indian manufacturing businesses' financial performance. Further, and Rakesh M (2013) examined the impact of capital structure on financial performance of Indian manufacturing companies and business companies listed on BSE, respectively, and found that capital structure had no effect on Return on Asset and Tobin's Q but had a significant negative impact on Return on Equity. Further, size, age, tangibles, sales growth, asset turnover, and ownership structure also affect Indian manufacturing enterprises' financial performance, according to Chadha & Sharma (2015). Another research studied the link between capital structure and performance of Indian companies listed on

NSE and showed that the firm's profitability had a negative correlation with capital structure because with increased level of debt in capital structure the chances of financial distress are more than the advantage of tax shield from debt. Another study by Gupta et al. (2011) indicated that capital structure negatively correlated with profitability of Indian companies listed on NSE because financial distress is more likely with larger debt levels than tax shield from debt. The systematic literature review Sachin Surana & Bankar (2020) analysed studies on capital structure and firm performance and found conflicting results. Tripathy and Singh (2018) used Fully Modified OLS and Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) to study BSE-listed firms over 18 years (2000–2017) and found that capital structure positively affects firm performance. Another study of Ghayas & Akhter, (2018) observed that short-term debt and total debt increased ROE, whereas long-term debt had little to no influence on Indian pharmaceutical firms

Cannoth & Jadheer (2020) study on Indian retail sector demonstrates that increasing debt negatively affects business performance and raises the danger of liquidity and insolvency, revealing a negative association between capital structure and Indian retail organisations. Patjoshi & Nandini (2020) found that total debt ratio and long-term debt ratio negatively affect Net Profit Margin, Return on Equity, Return on Total Assets, and Return on Investment, however only Net Profit Margin is significant.

Farhan et al. (2020) found that Indian service sector enterprises are more dependent on short-term debt than long-term debt. The study also found that short-term, long-term, and total debt hurt performance. The growth of pharmaceutical firms was linked to efficient capital structure Kumar & Priya (2021). The study on food processing companies Ahmad Khan (2015) found that capital structure, long-term debt, and liquid debt capital negatively affect corporate performance, while the study on Indian energy companies (Chakrabarti & Chakrabarti, 2019) found that profitability has no significant negative relationship with debt ratio. Another study of Nandini & Patjoshi (2020) examined how capital structure affects the financial performance of the top ten Indian automakers and observed that long-term debt, total debt, and funded debt to total capitalization ratio negatively affect Net Profit Margin, Return on Equity, Return on Total Assets, and Return on Investment, whereas Equity Ratio positively affects them. Malik & Singh, (2020) also identified a negative relationship between capital structure and financial performance in BSE Sensex businesses. Lower debt equity ratios improve capital structure. In a study of Indian tyre companies by Movalia (2015), capital structure (Debt-Equity Ratio) was found to be significantly related to profitability (Net Profit Ratio, ROI, ROCE), meaning that firms with an ideal capital structure (combination of debt and equity) make more money. Another study of Rani (2015) examined how capital structure affected financial performance of Indian listed businesses in the automobile, electronic, and metal industries. The capital structure did not affect financial performance in the vehicle sector but did in the electronic and metal sectors.

3. THEORETICAL MODEL

4. METHODOLOGY

The data collection starts with collecting data of 500 listed firms (both financial and non-financial) on National Stock Exchange (NSE) for a period of 21 years (2000-2021) using CMIE prowest database and then financial firms were excluded from the study because the laws applicable to them are different than the non-financial firm so the sample of 388 non-financial firms were identified across all industries from cement, pharmaceuticals, information technology, health services, textiles, steel and many more. Further, the panel was created out of the data collected of 388 non-financial firms and Pooled OLS Regression, Fixed and Random Effect regression was applied to know the impact of capital structure on performance of firms with various control variables. The study is in line with the studies of (Le & Phan, 2017), (Sheikh & Wang, 2013), (Dawar, 2014), (Hasan et al., 2014), (Ayange et al., 2021), (Saeedi & Mahmoodi, 2011).

The three regression Equations are:

$$ROA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_{i,t} + \beta_2 DMC_{i,t} + \beta_3 DTA_{i,t} + \beta_4 TAT_{i,t} + \beta_5 FAT_{i,t} + \beta_6 AGE_{i,t} + \beta_7 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_8 CR_{i,t} + \beta_9 CFO_{i,t} + \beta_{10} RG_{i,t} + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$RONW_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_{i,t} + \beta_2 DMC_{i,t} + \beta_3 DTA_{i,t} + \beta_4 TAT_{i,t} + \beta_5 FAT_{i,t} + \beta_6 AGE_{i,t} + \beta_7 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_8 CR_{i,t} + \beta_9 CFO_{i,t} + \beta_{10} RG_{i,t} + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$Tobin's Q_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_{i,t} + \beta_2 DMC_{i,t} + \beta_3 DTA_{i,t} + \beta_4 TAT_{i,t} + \beta_5 FAT_{i,t} + \beta_6 AGE_{i,t} + \beta_7 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_8 CR_{i,t} + \beta_9 CFO_{i,t} + \beta_{10} RG_{i,t} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where:

β_0 = Constant

β = Regression coefficient

ϵ_{it} = error term

4.1 Variables used in the study

Capital structure variables: The capital structure variables identified for the study are Debt Equity Ratio which is defined as total debt (short and long term) divided by total equity, Debt to Market Capitalization which is defined as total debt (short and long term) divided by NSE market capitalization of the company, Debt to Total Assets is calculated as total debt (short and long term) to total assets of the business. The firm capital structure refers to company funding from both internal and external sources of finance.

Performance Variables: Performance is measured with the help of three ratios Return on Net Worth which is calculated as Reported net profit for the year divided by the net worth of the company, Return on Total Assets is defined as Reported net profit for the year divided by the total assets of the company and Tobin’s Q is the indicator of measuring firm market performance and calculated as market capitalization to book value of the firm.

Control Variables: The control variables used in the study are size of the firm which is defined as log of total assets of the firm , firm’s age is defined as log of the total number of years since inception, total assets turnover is defined as sales for the year divided by total assets of the firm , fixed assets turnover is defined as sales for the year divided by total fixed assets of the firm, liquidity is calculated using current ratio which is defined as current assets divided by current liabilities, sales growth as calculated growth as of last year and cash flow to total assets is total cash flow from operating activities to total assets of the firm.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study regresses both accounting-Return on Net Worth, Return on Assets and market performance-Tobin’s Q variables with independent variables of capital structure as Debt Equity Ratio, Debt to Market Capitalization Ratio and Debt to Total Assets ratio and identified group of control variables using panel data analysis for a period of 21 years to examine the relationship between capital structure and measures of firm performance. Further, the Hausman test was applied to decide whether Fixed Effect Regression Model or Random Effect Regression Model is best suited for the regression analysis. The results of the Hausman test suggest that FEM is appropriate as the value is 0.000 which is less than 5%.

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

	DER	DMC	DTA	ROA	RONW	TOB_Q	TAT	FAT	AGE	SIZE	CR	CFO	RG
Mean	-0.34	-0.64	-0.72	7.016	14.57	1.44	1.09	4.92	1.51	4.37	1.44	0.093	28.08
Median	-0.25	-0.62	-0.62	6.24	14.05	0.90	0.95	2.05	1.51	4.33	1.19	0.09	12.88
Maximum	3.64	2.13	-0.08	115.83	1250.73	37.58	6.21	696.95	2.2	6.99	55.77	0.72	27650.74
Minimum	-2.00	-2.00	-2.00	-42.83	-525.11	0.00	0.01	-3171.55	0.30	2.40	0.02	-0.42	-89.12
Std. Dev.	0.54	0.75	0.40	7.04	28.82	1.70	0.70	55.66	0.27	0.70	1.46	0.083	525.51
Skewness	-0.36	0.059	-1.20	1.26	14.19	4.41	1.41	-37.82	-0.32	0.41	17.99	0.24	48.27
Kurtosis	4.14	2.59	4.06	21.25	775.99	56.11	6.17	2314.31	3.36	3.18	556.75	6.75	2371.11
Observations	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629	4629

DER: Debt Equity Ratio; **DMC:** Total Debt to Market Capitalization Ratio; **DTA:** Total Debt to Total Assets Ratio; **ROA:** Return on Assets=Profit by Total Assets; **RONW:** Return on Net Worth= Profit by Net Worth; **TOB_Q:** Tobin Q= Ratio of Market capitalization to Total Assets; **TAT:** Total Assets Turnover; **FAT:** Fixed Assets Turnover Ratio; **Age:** Firm Age; **Size:** Firm Size; **CR:** Current Ratio; **CFO:** Cash flow to Total Assets Ratio; **RG:** Revenue Growth

The Table 5.1 indicates that the descriptive statistics for the data collected between years 2000 to 2020 for all the variables of Capital Structure variables namely (Debt Equity Ratio, Debt to Market Capitalization and Debt to Total Assets and variables of performance namely ROA, RONW, Tobin’ Q and all the control variables. The mean value of capital structure variable ranges from

-0.34 To -0.72, performance variables mean range from 1.44 to 14.57 and control variables mean range from 0.093 to 28.08. The standard deviation of DER, DMC and DTA is low which shows that there is not much deviation in the value of capital structure ratios. The S.D. values of RONW are very high which shows high variations in the value of RONW while ROA and Tobin Q has low variations. The control variables FAT, RG have more variations in its value as compared to other control variables like TAT, Age, Size, CR and CFO.

5.2 Correlation Matrix

	DER	DMC	DTA	ROA	RONW	TOB_Q	TAT	FAT	AGE	SIZE	CR	CFO	RG
DER	1.00												
DMC	0.82	1.00											
DTA	0.94	0.79	1.00										
ROA	-0.46	-0.53	-0.39	1.00									
RONW	-0.19	-0.25	-0.13	0.57	1.00								
TOB_Q	-0.31	-0.65	-0.27	0.38	0.17	1.00							
TAT	-0.03	-0.13	-0.11	0.25	0.19	0.13	1.00						
FAT	0.00	-0.01	-0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.15	1.00					
AGE	-0.05	-0.03	-0.06	-0.06	-0.06	-0.05	-0.01	-0.05	1.00				
SIZE	0.05	-0.01	0.04	-0.12	-0.07	-0.04	-0.23	0.03	0.20	1.00			
CR	-0.34	-0.24	-0.30	0.16	0.03	0.08	-0.08	0.00	-0.01	-0.06	1.00		
CFO	-0.18	-0.20	-0.17	0.42	0.27	0.14	0.20	-0.05	-0.01	-0.10	0.00	1.00	
RG	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.00	-0.06	0.01	-0.02	0.00	1.00

DER: Debt Equity Ratio; **DMC:** Total Debt to Market Capitalization Ratio; **DTA:** Total Debt to Total Assets Ratio; **ROA:** Return on Assets=Profit by Total Assets; **RONW:** Return on Net Worth= Profit by Net Worth; **TOB_Q:** Tobin Q= Ratio of Market capitalization to Total Assets; **TAT:** Total Assets Turnover; **FAT:** Fixed Assets Turnover Ratio; **Age:** Firm Age; **Size:** Firm Size; **CR:** Current Ratio; **CFO:** Cash flow to Total Assets Ratio; **RG:** Revenue Growth

The Table 5.2 indicates the Correlation between the variables of Capital Structure and Firm Performance. The correlation matrix indicates high degree of positive correlation between various variables of capital structure as measured by Debt-to-Equity Ratio, Debt to Market Capitalization and Debt to Total Assets. The correlation between Debt-to-Equity ratio and Debt to Market Capitalization is 0.82 and between Debt to Equity and Debt to Total Assets 0.92 and between Debt to Total Assets and Debt to Market Capitalization is 0.79. It can also be observed that the Firm Performance variable ROA, RONW and Tobin Q all are negatively correlated to all the Capital Structure variables measured by Debt Equity Ratio, Debt to Market Capitalization and Debt to Total Assets Ratio. The other control variables Total Assets Turnover, Fixed Assets Turnover, Firm age, Current Ratio, Cash Flow to Total Assets all have negative and low degree of correlation with Capital Structure variables.

Firstly, the Pooled OLS Regression is performed, taking each variable of Firm Performance as a Dependent variable. Individual effects of the variables of Capital Structure namely, DER, DMC and DTA is taken into consideration on each dependent variable, for the pooled OLS Regression Analysis.

5.3 The Effect of CS on performance of non-financial firms listed on NSE: Ordinary Least Square Method (OLS)

	Dependent Variable: ROA			Dependent Variable: RONW			Dependent Variable: Tobin's Q		
	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA
DER	-4.34 (.000)**	--	--	-2.623 (.019)*	--	--	-1.496 (.000)**	--	--
DMC	--	-4.307 (.000)**	--	--	-11.46 (0.000)**	--	--	-1.456 (.000)**	--
DTA	--	--	-7.243 (.000)**	--	--	-5.692 (.006)**	--	--	-1.918 (.000)**
TAT	1.614 (.000)**	1.35 (.000)**	1.445 (.000)**	2.595 (.004)**	5.178 (.000)**	2.317 (.006)**	0.372 (.000)**	0.082 (.005)**	0.250 (.000)**
FAT	-0.002 (.231)	-0.001 (.379)	-0.005 (.041)*	0.006 (.665)	0.002 (.889)	-0.007 (.705)	-0.000 (.390)	-0.000 (.422)	-0.001 (.390)
RG	9.180 (.532)	0.000 (.462)	-0.000 (.000)**	4.520 (.971)	-0.000 (.815)	-0.000 (.889)	4.00 (.581)	3.240 (.302)	1.390 (.822)
CFO	32.125 (.000)**	30.749 (.000)**	8.866 (.000)**	92.554 (.000)**	79.307 (.000)**	100.83 (.000)**	2.147 (.000)**	-0.451 (.051)	1.602 (.000)**
AGE	-1.745 (.000)**	-1.407 (.000)**	-0.346 (.416)	-7.79 (0.002)**	-3.378 (.278)	-6.674 (.069)	-0.691 (.000)**	-0.445 (.000)**	-0.715 (.000)**
SIZE	-0.085 (.462)	-0.359 (.006)*	-0.052 (.756)	-1.657 (.089)	0.215 (.862)	-0.975 (.456)	0.007 (.898)	-0.087 (.002)**	-0.052 (.342)
CR	0.387 (.000)**	0.354 (.000)**	0.482 (.000)**	0.270 (.000)**	-0.120 (.835)	0.674 (.272)	-0.058 (.027)*	-0.092 (.000)**	-0.045 (.081)
Constant	3.292 (.000)**	2.952 (.000)**	-0.896 (.307)	22.108 (.000)**	-2.633 (.705)	10.864 (.114)	1.585 (.000)**	1.659 (.000)**	1.162 (.000)**
Observations	5905	4729	5919	5897	4665	5813	5054	4728	5037
Adjusted R ²	0.397	0.421	0.238	0.036	0.050	0.024	0.146	0.419	0.130
F-test	486.993	430.492	232.111	28.907	31.747	18.794	109.059	426.630	94.902
p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

(p-values in the bracket); *significant at 5% level **significant at 1%; -- no value

DER: Debt Equity Ratio; **DMC:** Total Debt to Market Capitalization Ratio; **DTA:** Total Debt to Total Assets Ratio; **ROA:** Return on Assets=Profit by Total Assets; **RONW:** Return on Net Worth= Profit by Net Worth; **TOB_Q:** Tobin Q= Ratio of Market capitalization to Total Assets; **TAT:** Total Assets Turnover; **FAT:** Fixed Assets Turnover Ratio; **Age:** Firm Age; **Size:** Firm Size; **CR:** Current Ratio; **CFO:** Cash flow to Total Assets Ratio; **RG:** Revenue Growth

The Table 5.3 indicates that the Capital Structure variables DER, DMC and DTA are negatively related to the ROA variable of the Firm Performance as the standardized coefficient estimators are -4.34, -4.307 and -7.243 respectively. The p-value is same at 0.000 in all the three variables (DER, DMC and DTC), which is less than 0.05 and it is statistically significant and shows that capital structure has a significant negative impact on firm performance as measured by ROA. Capital Structure variables DER, DMC and DTC are also negatively related to the RONW variable of the Firm Performance as the standardized coefficient estimators are -2.623, -11.46, and -5.692 respectively. The p-value for the same is 0.019, 0.000 and 0.006 respectively which is less than 0.05. Hence it is statistically significant and shows that capital structure has a significant negative impact on firm performance as measured by RONW. The Tobin's Q variable of Firm Performance, all three variables of the Capital Structure namely, DER, DMC and DTA are negatively related as the standardized coefficient estimator is -1.496, -1.456 and -1.918 respectively. The p-value for the variables DTA and DMC is 0.000 in all the cases, which is less than 0.05. Hence it is statistically significant and shows that capital structure has a significant negative impact on firm performance as measured by Tobin's Q.

5.4 The Effect of CS on performance of non-financial firms listed on NSE: Fixed Effect Regression (FEM)

	Dependent Variable: ROA			Dependent Variable: RONW			Dependent Variable: Tobin's Q		
	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA
DER	-3.943 (.000)**	--	--	-0.153 (.925)	--	--	-0.930 (.000)**	--	--
DMC	--	-4.788 (.000)**	--	--	-17.52 (0.000)**	--	--	-1.283 (.000)**	--
DTA	--	--	-6.408 (.000)**	--	--	-1.646 (.592)	--	--	-1.163 (.000)**
TAT	5.29 (.000)**	5.05 (.000)**	5.670 (.000)**	14.03 (.000)**	13.169 (.000)**	14.41 (.000)**	0.593 (.000)**	0.000 (.311)	0.573 (.000)**
FAT	-2.860 (.985)	-0.001 (.896)	-0.001 (.601)	0.004 (.780)	-0.003 (.852)	0.005 (.792)	-9.01 (.886)	0.000 (.665)	-6.22 (.992)
RG	0.000 (.378)	5.390 (.653)	-0.000 (.011)*	0.000 (.863)	0.000 (.799)	0.000 (.792)	6.15 (.291)	2.49 (.290)	6.00 (.226)
CFO	16.965 (.000)**	13.424 (.000)**	5.040 (.000)**	57.35 (.000)**	41.53 (.000)**	64.72 (.000)**	1.241 (.003)**	0.224 (.276)	1.500 (.000)**
AGE	-4.831 (.000)**	-7.65 (.000)**	-3.964 (.010)**	-5.62 (0.609)	-19.537 (.213)	-9.881 (.512)	0.438 (.414)	-1.165 (.000)**	0.701 (.186)
SIZE	1.497 (.000)**	0.321 (.408)	2.127 (.000)**	-0.215 (.944)	1.157 (.799)	4.613 (.270)	0.622 (.000)**	0.526 (.000)**	0.597 (.000)**
CR	0.153 (.006)**	0.116 (.071)	0.209 (.000)**	0.471 (.390)	-0.626 (.400)	0.855 (.251)	-0.002 (.949)	-0.055 (.000)**	0.007 (.802)
Constant	-1.145 (.249)	6.990 (.000)**	-8.307 (.000)**	3.913 (.688)	-9.281 (.536)	-14.70 (.252)	-2.791 (.000)**	0.093 (.711)	-3.637 (.000)**
Observations	5905	4729	5919	5897	4665	5813	5054	4728	5037
Adjusted R ²	0.602	0.620	0.542	0.131	0.070	0.093	0.481	0.694	0.475
F-test	23.857	21.345	18.964	3.276	1.932	2.518	13.091	29.383	12.791
p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Hausman Test P value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

(p-values in the bracket); *significant at 5% level **significant at 1%; -- no value

DER: Debt Equity Ratio; **DMC:** Total Debt to Market Capitalization Ratio; **DTA:** Total Debt to Total Assets Ratio; **ROA:** Return on Assets=Profit by Total Assets; **RONW:** Return on Net Worth= Profit by Net Worth; **TOB_Q:** Tobin Q= Ratio of Market capitalization to Total Assets; **TAT:** Total Assets Turnover; **FAT:** Fixed Assets Turnover Ratio; **Age:** Firm Age; **Size:** Firm Size; **CR:** Current Ratio; **CFO:** Cash flow to Total Assets Ratio; **RG:** Revenue Growth

The Fixed Effect Regression is performed, taking each variable of Firm Performance as a Dependent variable. Individual effects of the variables of Capital Structure namely, DER, DMC and DTA is taken into consideration on each Dependent variable, for the Fixed Effect Regression Analysis.

The above Table 5.4 indicates that the capital structure variables DER, DMC and DTA are negatively related to the ROA variable of the Firm Performance as the standardized coefficient estimator is -3.943, -4.788 and -6.408 respectively. The p-value is same which is 0.000 in all the three variables (DER, DMC and DTA), which is less than 0.05 and it is statistically significant and shows that capital structure has a significant negative impact on firm performance measured by ROA. Capital Structure variables DER, DMC and DTA are also negatively related to the RONW variable of the Firm Performance as the standardized coefficient estimators are -0.153, -17.52, and -1.646 respectively. The p-value for the same is 0.925, 0.000 and 0.592 respectively. The p-value is statistically significant only with DMC which shows that capital structure as measured by DMC has a significant negative impact on firm performance as measured by RONW. The Tobin's Q variable of the Firm Performance is negatively related to all three variables of the Capital Structure namely, DER, DMC

and DTA as the standardized coefficient estimator is -0.930, -1.283 and -1.163 respectively and the p-value for all the three variables, DER, DMC and DMC are at 0.000 in all the cases, which is less than 0.05 which is statistically significant and shows that capital structure has an impact of capital structure on firm performance as measured by Tobin's Q.

5.5 The Effect of CS on performance of non-financial firms listed on NSE: Random Effect Regression (REM)

	Dependent Variable: ROA			Dependent Variable: RONW			Dependent Variable: Tobin's Q		
	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA	Log of DER	Log of DMC	Log of DTA
DER	-4.184 (.000)**	--	--	-2.033 (.113)	--	--	-1.110 (.000)**	--	--
DMC	--	-4.613 (.000)**	--	--	-11.92 (0.000)**	--	--	-1.361 (.000)**	--
DTA	--	--	-6.139 (.000)**	--	--	-5.304 (.024)*	--	--	-1.398 (.000)**
TAT	3.375 (.000)**	2.928 (.000)**	3.853 (.000)**	5.028 (.000)**	5.438 (.000)**	4.107 (.007)**	0.547 (.000)**	0.079 (0.058)	0.508 (.000)**
FAT	-0.002 (.304)	-0.001 (.426)	-0.000 (.733)	0.002 (.880)	-0.003 (.852)	0.003 (.853)	-0.000 (.659)	3.35 (.907)	-0.000 (.789)
RG	0.000 (.347)	-4.00 (.737)	-0.000 (.003)**	0.000 (.913)	0.000 (.957)	0.000 (.845)	4.89 (.399)	2.24 (.340)	4.42 (.371)
CFO	21.650 (.000)**	20.398 (.000)**	5.869 (.000)**	78.66 (.000)**	77.137 (.000)**	89.50 (.000)**	1.329 (.001)**	-0.070 (.725)	1.479 (.000)**
AGE	-2.040 (.000)**	-2.631 (.000)**	-0.482 (.543)	-8.166 (0.021)*	-3.461 (.296)	-6.533 (.143)	-0.202 (.468)	-6.628 (.000)**	-0.092 (.737)
SIZE	0.316 (.062)	-0.471 (.014)*	0.751 (.003)**	-1.567 (.229)	0.298 (.820)	-0.240 (.886)	0.444 (.000)**	0.231 (.000)**	0.440 (.000)**
CR	0.257 (.000)**	0.227 (.000)**	0.307 (.000)**	0.366 (.459)	-0.152 (.797)	0.747 (.255)	-0.003 (.896)	-0.059 (.000)**	0.005 (.830)
Constant	1.226 (.114)	4.316 (.000)**	-6.139 (.000)**	21.15 (.001)**	-3.352 (.646)	-7.698 (.352)	-0.927 (.026)*	0.613 (.004)**	-1.700 (.000)**
Observations	5905	4729	5919	5897	4665	5813	5054	4728	5037
Adjusted R ²	0.304	0.354	0.203	0.026	0.049	0.017	0.079	0.361	0.076
F-test	323.513	326.005	189.846	20.347	30.933	13.841	55.033	335.365	52.813
p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Hausman Test P value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

(p-values in the bracket); *significant at 5% level **significant at 1%; -- no value

DER: Debt Equity Ratio; **DMC:** Total Debt to Market Capitalization Ratio; **DTA:** Total Debt to Total Assets Ratio; **ROA:** Return on Assets=Profit by Total Assets; **RONW:** Return on Net Worth= Profit by Net Worth; **TOB_Q:** Tobin Q= Ratio of Market capitalization to Total Assets; **TAT:** Total Assets Turnover; **FAT:** Fixed Assets Turnover Ratio; **Age:** Firm Age; **Size:** Firm Size; **CR:** Current Ratio; **CFO:** Cash flow to Total Assets Ratio; **RG:** Revenue Growth

The Random Effect Regression is performed, taking each variable of Firm Performance as a Dependent variable. Individual effects of the variables of Capital Structure namely, DER, DMC and DTA is measured on each Dependent variable, for the Random Effect Regression Analysis.

The above Table 5.5 indicates that the Capital Structure variables DER, DMC and DTA are negatively related to the ROA variable of the Firm Performance as the standardized coefficient estimator is -4.184, -4.613 and -6.139 respectively. The p-value for the same at 0.000 in all the three variables (DER, DMC and DTA) which is less than 0.05 which is statistically significant and shows that capital structure has a significant negative impact on firm performance measured by ROA. Capital Structure variables DER, DMC and DTC are also negatively related to the RONW variable of the Firm Performance as the standardized coefficient estimators are -2.033, -11.92, and -5.304 respectively.

The p-value for the same is 0.113, 0.000 and 0.294 respectively. The p-value is statistically significant only with DMC and DTA which shows capital structure as measured by DMC and DTA has an impact on firm performance as measured by RONW. The Tobin's Q variable of the Firm Performance is negatively related to all three variables of the Capital Structure namely, DER, DMC and DTA as the standardized coefficient estimator is -1.110, -1.361 and -1.398 respectively and the p-value for all the three variables, DER, DMC and DMC are at 0.000 in all the three variables (DER, DMC and DTA) which is statistically significant and shows that capital structure has an impact of capital structure on firm performance as measured by Tobin's Q.

6. CONCLUSION

This study reveals that capital structure variables—Debt Equity Ratio, Debt to Market Capitalization ratio, and Debt to Total Assets ratio—have a negative association with accounting and market metrics of business performance—Return on Equity, Return on Net Worth, and Tobin's Q. Capital structure negatively affects performance with control factors like size, liquidity, age, revenue growth, cash flow, total assets turnover, and fixed assets turnover, according to Pooled OLS results. The Fixed Effect Regression Model and Random Effect Regression Model likewise reveal a significant negative influence on Debt Equity Ratio, Debt to Market Capitalization, Debt to Total Assets, Return on Equity, and Tobin's Q, but not on Return on Net Worth. The Pooled OLS, REM and FEM results are in consistent with the results of (Le & Phan, 2017), (Vätavu, 2015), (Rakesh M, 2013), (Sheikh & Wang, 2013), (Dawar, 2014), (Hasan et al., 2014), (M, 2013), (Zeitun & Tian, 2007) and (M.González, 2013). Capital structure harms Indian non-financial firms. Companies' limited ability to raise equity capital in an emerging country like India, where debt borrowing is quicker, cheaper, and the standard for existing enterprises, is a crucial factor. Due to changing economic policies, regulatory landscape, and reasonably high yields in the country, debt negatively impacts capital structure ratios and company financial performance. Financial managers, lenders, investors, and policymakers will all benefit from this research. Research shows that managers of financial institutions should take into account how debt levels affect performance before making any changes in debt levels of the capital structure. Lenders should examine all debt agreements carefully in light of the impact on the performance of the firm they are lending to. Before making an investment, investors should consider the company's sustainable debt level and its ability to generate free cash flow. Lastly, policy makers should bestow their guidance based on the implication of monetary and regulatory policies over various rates – Benchmark rates, small savings, pensions, lending rates, etc which have wider implications over eventual debt component of capital structure for firms.

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